

VIBRATION DAMPING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 4-AXIALLY REINFORCED 3D COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A 4-Axially reinforced 3D composite impregnated with flexible epoxy resin is a new and unique damper(3D-Sole, 3D-Sole is a registered trademark)which is possible to increase the vibration damping in structure without significant reductions in stiffness and strength. In this study mechanical properties, compressive strength and creep strain, were examined first and then the vibration damping characteristics, such as a loss factor, a resonant frequency, a resonance curve and a damping coefficient, were obtained experimentally. Based on the experiments, remarkable properties of 3D-Sole have been verified: compressive strength is 30 times compared with the conventional damper; the loss factor and the damping coefficient are 0.5 and 23%, respectively; the creep velocity is about 3×10^{-5} %/h at room temperature; the specific gravity is 1.7. 3D-Sole has been found to be promising for reducing the vibration of heavy equipment.

1.INTRODUCTION

Recently, because of many problems associated with the uncontrolled vibration, such as earthquake damage to buildings, damage to sensitive electronic equipment, passenger discomfort in vehicles, occupant discomfort in buildings, positioning errors in magnetic disk of a computer and so on, there have been strong needs in the field of industrial equipment towards low noise and low vibration coupled with an environmental concern. Several technologies are conventionally used to reduce the troublesome vibrations including adding rubber or viscoelastic materials to absorb vibrations by converting kinetic energy to thermal energy(passive damping) and using electrical sensors and actuators to control vibrations by inducing the reverse phase vibration(active damping). Passive damping technologies are especially frequently used in the field of industrial equipment for reasons of low cost and simplicity. In composite structures, several passive damping technologies, Barrett's shear-coupled damped cylinder concept[1], BYU's advanced concept[2], have been attempted as the improved Constrained Layer Damping(CLD) concept[3]. However, these technologies have not taken into account the damping of the multi-axial vibrations as actually observed in structures, and are not suitable for the vibration damping of heavy equipment for reasons of load resistance .

In this paper, a newly developed 3D composite damper "3D-Sole", 3D-Sole is a registered trademark, which has characteristics of horizontal vibration damping not only the vertical in

structure without significant reductions in load and creep resistance is demonstrated by the experimental results of mechanical and vibration damping properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

Fig.1 represents the geometry of 3D-Sole. 3D-Sole is composed of the reinforcements and the matrix resin. In this experiment, unidirectionally reinforced GFRP(E-glass fiber reinforced vinyl ester resin) rods of average length and diameter, 280mm and 1.8mm, respectively were used as the reinforcements, and the flexible epoxy resin exhibiting rubberlike elasticity at room temperature was used as the matrix resin.

The forming process of 3D-Sole is illustrated in Fig.2. First, the reinforcements are manually assembled by piercing to the orientation defined by the 4 longest diagonals of the cube. Secondly, the three-dimensionally assembled reinforcements are impregnated with the deaerated matrix resin under vacuum. Finally, the matrix resin is cured at a temperature of 100 °C for 4 hours.

Four kinds of specimens were cut out from the formed sample above-mentioned to evaluate the dependence of the specimen shapes on vibration damping properties. Shapes and dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig.3.

2.2 TEST METHODS

3D-Sole is supposed to be used mainly under condition of compressive loading. Therefore, compression tests, compressive creep tests and compression-compression fatigue tests were carried out to obtain mechanical properties. Vibration damping characteristics were evaluated by the resonance method.

A universal material testing machine(Instron,Type1185) was used for the compression tests at a crosshead speed of 1.0mm/min. In the compression tests, a mean yield strength to assure load-resistance was initially obtained through the iterations of loading and unloading to five specimens of typeB in Fig.3, and the mean ultimate strength was finally obtained.

The creep test was carried out under a compressive load of 460N(stress:3Mpa) to a specimen of typeB in Fig.3 at room temperature. Creep strains up to 500 hours were measured and creep velocity was obtained to estimate long-term behavior by extrapolation toward the gradient level.

Compression-compression fatigue tests were performed at room temperature. Sinusoidal cycles of 10^4 times were loaded under compressive load of 13.2kN maximum and 1.5kN minimum on 0.2Hz to a specimen of typeC in Fig.3. Equivalent damping coefficients defined as shown in Fig.4 were obtained from the load-deflection loops measured at sufficient time intervals. Maximum and minimum deflections of each cycle were measured to define the creep effects. A yield strength and an ultimate strength of the tested specimen were also obtained to clear the fatigue effects on the strength.

Vibration damping characteristics, resonance frequency and loss factors, were obtained from resonance curve with resonance magnification(ratio of input and output amplitude) plotted as the ordinate and frequency as the abscissa. Fig.5 shows the measuring system of the resonance method. Three specimens were set on the base and then to define the dependence of a stress on a

resonance frequency, a mass was put on the specimens in order. Accelerometers were attached on the base and the mass, and sinusoidal vibration of 0.4G was loaded sweeping from 5Hz to 400Hz. The specimens of type A, B and D in Fig.3 were used to clarify the dependence of a shape factor (as defined in Fig.3) on a resonance frequency.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical load-deflection loop in elastic deformation and a load-deflection curve up to the ultimate strength are shown in Fig.6 and 7. It is obvious from the Fig.6 that the behavior of large energy absorption, caused by viscoelastic characteristics of the matrix, was observed as shown in the hysteresis loop. Fig.8 shows a SEM photograph of the cross section through the specimen applied several iterations of loading and unloading in elastic deformation. Any cracks and debondings are not observed at the interface of the matrix and the reinforcements. This indicates 3D-Sole deforms against the compressive load keeping the strong adhesive bonding between the reinforcements and the matrix. A mean yield strength and a ultimate strength were 13Mpa and 200Mpa. The load resistance of 6.5Mpa was determined in consideration of the safety margin from this result.

Fig.9 indicates the creep strains up to 500 hours at room temperature. In the figure, zero position of creep strain is defined as the strain at the instant of the loading. Creep strains increase slightly and approach 2% at 500 hours. Long-term creep strain can be estimated by extrapolation toward the gradient level as shown in Fig.10. From a result of the estimation, it is obvious that creep velocity is only 3×10^{-5} %/h and a creep strain at 2×10^4 hours is about 2.8%. A conventional rubber damper of low creep type indicates about 3% at 2×10^4 hours, although loading condition is only 1MPa. As obvious from these results, 3D-Sole has suitable properties for the damping of heavy equipment.

Load-deflection loops at 1, 100 and 10^4 cycles in the fatigue tests are shown in (a), (b) and (c) of Fig.11, respectively. Equivalent damping coefficient h_{eq} represents the magnitude of viscous damping gradually decreases with increasing numbers of cycles keeping a high damping level as shown in Fig.12. This level is almost equal to that of the laminate rubber damper of a high damping type. The variation of the maximum and the minimum deflections of each cycle are shown in Fig.13. The effect of creep strain is about 3% at 10^4 cycles. A yield strength and an ultimate strength were also obtained from the specimen applied fatigue loading and the results show that the fatigue loading has little effect on these strengths.

Typical resonance curves with resonance magnification μ plotted as the ordinate and frequency as the abscissa in vertical and horizontal vibration are shown in (a) and (b) of Fig.14. The remarkable results in these curves are these; resonance magnification at resonant frequency is restrained to a low level, approximately 2.0, in both directions; loss factor indicates the vibration damping performance is about 0.55. Isotropic properties of resonance magnifications in both directions are supposed to be due to the three-dimensional orientation of the reinforcements in 3D-Sole as explained in Fig.1. Like the h_{eq} , the loss factor of 3D-Sole is almost equal to that of the damper of a high damping type. Fig.15 shows the dependence of the shape factor and compressive stress on the resonant frequency. Actual damping design of 3D-Sole is carried out by using calibrated curves as shown in this figure. 3D-Sole has a characteristic of high stiffness, therefore the minimum resonant frequency, capable of design, is considered to be higher compared with the conventional rubber damper.

4. CONCLUSION

Mechanical and vibration damping properties of a newly developed damper "3D-Sole" have been presented experimentally in this paper. 3D-Sole has remarkable characteristics suitable for the vibration damping of heavy equipment: the specific gravity is 1.7; the load resistance is 6.5MPa; the creep velocity is about 3×10^{-5} %/h; the loss factor is 0.55; and the damping coefficient is 23%. Resistance to environmental circumstances, such as heat resistance, oil resistance and weather resistance, will be evaluated continuously.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1. The geometry of 3D-Sole.

Figure 2. The forming process of 3D-Sole.

Fig.3 Shapes and dimensions of the specimens.

Equivalent damping coefficient $h_{eq} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\text{area of the loop} \text{ (shaded)}}{\text{area of elastic energy} \text{ (black)}}$

Fig.4 The definition of equivalent damping coefficient.

Fig.5 The measuring system of the resonance method.

Fig.6 A typical load-deflection loop

Fig.7 A typical load-deflection curve

Fig.8 SEM photograph of the cross section of the specimen loaded in the elastic deformation.

Fig.9. The creep strain of 3D-Sole.

Fig.10 The creep velocity of 3D-Sole.

Fig.11 Load-deflection loops in compression-compression fatigue tests.

Fig.12 The variation of the equivalent damping coefficient in the fatigue tests.

Fig.13 The variation of the deflection in the fatigue tests.

Fig.14 Typical resonance curves in vertical and horizontal vibration

Fig.15 The dependence of the shape factors and the compressive stress on the resonant frequency.